
Deliverable D4.1

Plan for dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement

Editor(s):	J. Favaro, J. Arteza, Z. Smith, A. Petrocelli
Responsible Partner:	Trust-IT
Status-Version:	Final - v1.0
Date:	31/12/2020
Distribution level (CO, PU):	PU

Project Number:	GA 957044
Project Title:	SWForum.eu

Title of Deliverable:	Plan for dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement
Due Date of Delivery to the EC	31.12.2020

Workpackage responsible for the Deliverable:	WP4 - Communication, Dissemination and MTRL
Editor(s):	Trust-IT
Contributor(s):	TECNALIA
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Approved by:	All Partners
Recommended/mandatory readers:	WP1-4

Abstract:	This report outlines stakeholder groups & targeted engagement activities.
Keyword List:	Software, cybersecurity, infrastructure, outreach, podcast, workshop, branding
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Document Description

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v0.1	16.11.2020	Draft Table of Contents and text contributions	John Favaro
v0.2	14.12.2020	Comments and suggestions received by consortium partners, in particular internal consortium quality review by Tecnalia.	ALL
V0.3	22.12.2020	Final version after modifications as a result of the internal consortium quality review	J. Alonso, J. Arteza, Z. Smith, J. Favaro
V1.0	22.12.2020	Ready for submission	Leire Orue-Echevarria (TECNALIA)

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Terms and abbreviations

CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team
CMS	Content Management System
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DG	Directorate General
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DoA	Description of Action
DSM	Digital Single Market
EBN	European Business and Innovation Centres Network
EC	European Commission
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
ETP	European Technology Platform
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ISO	International Standards Organisation
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MS	Member State
MTRL	Market Technology Readiness Level
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
SME	Small to Medium Enterprise
SW	Software
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community

Executive Summary

Consistent and content-rich communication is strategic to showcasing the results and impact of the objectives and goals within SWForum.eu. This plan presents the activities to be put in place by the consortium during the 30 months of the project. This plan has been built on a series of communication and promotional campaigns for the main SWForum.eu assets, primarily: the SWForum.eu Forum, SWForum.eu community of stakeholders, the Project Radar, and the Mini-Sites. The custom-made SWForum.eu Platform is at the core of the engagement, outreach and exploitation strategy of the project; it is the technological engine behind the Project Radar, the Mini-Sites, and support for the Living Forum.

Various communication and promotional campaigns are presented in this plan, with detailed timelines presenting the activities that will be put in place. For each of these campaigns, specific communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities targeting identified stakeholder groups are presented to ensure the successful achievements of the project objectives.

Section 1 of the plan presents the project objectives and the communication activities that will support them.

Section 2 presents the project communication and stakeholder engagement strategy and the key project assets.

Section 3 illustrates the SWForum.eu stakeholders group, with clear benefits for them in engaging with the project.

Section 4 introduces the Project Radar and Mini-Sites facility, together with the procedures followed for outreach and engagement of projects.

Section 5 brings us within the core communication, dissemination, marketing and stakeholders activities with details on how to engage and communicate with target stakeholders and includes associated KPIs for monitoring the activities and the impact.

Section 6 continues with an overview of SWForum.eu organisation and participation to events.

Section 7 offers a list on the overall communication and engagement tools and channels to be used to make the plan as pragmatic as possible, including online presence and content production, collaterals and social media channel utilisation and distribution.

Section 8 presents the online dashboard monitoring the visibility, engagement, and dissemination potential of online activities in automated software that will be used through the entire project duration.

An Appendix provides the preliminary list of events being monitored by SWForum.eu.

This is only the first of three versions of the Plan for dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement. All of the key instruments of engagement, including the Project Radar, Mini-Sites, Living Forum, Webinars, Podcasts, Events List, and so forth, will be updated in successive versions (M18, M30) of this document in order to track the progress of these outreach activities. Specifically, activities around the rollout of MTRL training will be taken up in further versions of the document, as they start up in the project; likewise, numerous stakeholder engagement activities will start up and be reported in the next version of the document. Finally, the list of events will be updated as clarity begins to arrive around the many transformation of events occurring due to the ongoing Covid-19 crisis.

1 Background and objectives

The purpose of this document is to put in place a pragmatic communication, dissemination & stakeholder engagement plan for SWForum.eu to be delivered through diverse communication channels over the 30-month duration of the project.

1.1 Document structure

Section 1 of the plan presents the project objectives and the communication activities that will support them.

Section 2 presents the project communication and stakeholder engagement strategy and the key project assets.

Section 3 illustrates the SWForum.eu stakeholders group, with clear benefits for them in engaging with the project.

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Section 8 presents the online dashboard monitoring the visibility, engagement, and dissemination potential of online activities in automated software that will be used through the entire project duration.

An **Appendix** presents the current list of relevant events being planned or tracked by SWForum.eu.

1.2 Relation with other project deliverables

The following deliverables of SWForum.eu are related to this document:

- D1.2 – this is the project-wide risk assessment and contingency plan. Section 9 provides a specific extension for WP4-related risks.
- D2.1, D2.2, D2.3-3 – Cross-fertilization workshop reports. See Section 6.1 for a more comprehensive discussion of the workshops.
- D3.1, D3.2 – Landscape Reports. These reports will be significant dissemination items which will be communicated on the SWForum.eu social channels. See also Section 3.6 for a discussion of the major target stakeholders of these reports.
- D3.3, D3.4, D3.5 – Software Forum Research Roadmaps. Analogous to the above, these will be major dissemination items within the outreach on social media channels. See also Sections 3.2 and 3.6 for indications of the principal target stakeholders.
- D3.6, D3.7, D3.8 – Reports on Fellowship programme, governance structure, and business model for SWForum.eu. These reports will be particularly pertinent to major SWForum.eu stakeholders in industry. See Sections 3.1, 3.3, and 3.5 for more discussion.

- D4.2, D4.3 – Reports on dissemination, communication & stakeholder engagement. These two deliverables will provide timely updates to the present document as the project progresses.

1.3 Specific objectives

The specific objectives of this plan for communication & stakeholder engagement and promotion of the open calls are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Specific Objectives

Objective	Main Target Activities
Deliver and maintain a plan for communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Guarantee sharing of information and engagement via webinars & events, including ones to be held online; □ Establish key strategic partnerships with SWForum.eu-related projects, leveraging on the partners enrolled in the project as first multipliers; □ Produce and distribute information & marketing materials; □ Design and maintain an editorial plan including all relevant communications material and channels.
Showcase SWForum.eu results, creating awareness of the impact of the Living Forum, the Project Radar and its associated mini-sites, and the cross-fertilization workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Organisation of regular cross-fertilization workshops; □ Creation of webinars and podcasts with high-profile experts in the SWForum.eu target disciplines; □ Provide enhanced online visibility for the projects and other actors engaged via the Project Radar and mini-sites.
Ensure global recognition and visibility on how the EU is pursuing world-class research in software engineering, infrastructure, and cybersecurity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Support the delivery of SWForum.eu Landscape Reports. □ Create a lasting legacy community of EU experts and engaged actors within the SWForum.eu Living Forum, including researchers and research organisations, policy makers, and industry representatives, especially SMEs.
Ensure a proper branding strategy and recognition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Equip all partners with information and marketing materials for outreach purposes to the specific target audiences; □ Ensure alignment and collaboration with the H2020 projects and initiatives.

2 SWForum.eu Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

SWForum.eu will execute a coordinated 30-month communication strategy covering the design, set-up and management of the 1) the SWForum.eu platform, 2) the Living Forum, 3) the set-up a community of stakeholders interested in the opportunities offered by the "mini-sites" and the 4) project's outreach and support. These represent the key assets of the SWForum.eu communication & stakeholders engagement campaigns (Figure 1).

Figure 1: SWForum.eu Communication Campaigns

1. **SWForum.eu platform.** The platform will be the central point of access for the major SWforum.eu activities and initiatives. It will be developed, hosted and managed by partner TRUST-IT, providing the basis for the initiatives outlined in the following.
2. **Living Forum.** The platform will provide a Living Forum where researchers, industry representatives and end users will be able share their content and knowledge (e.g. webinars, opinion articles, best practices...).
3. **User Community.** The platform will also be enhanced with 1) a technology radar, presenting for the funded projects in the topics of software technologies and cloud spanning from 2016 – 2024, both the technology landscape location maturity and readiness for market; and 2) with a hub of project mini-sites containing a complete, unabridged and updated compilation of EU-funded research projects on software topics.
4. **Communication and stakeholder engagement campaigns.** Potential stakeholders from a diversity of groups will be approached through targeted campaigns and communication instruments, ranging from news articles, social media outreach, and events to podcasts, interviews, and videos.

The associated campaigns will be implemented via a series of communication and dissemination activities that are detailed in Section 5 of this document.

The dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement plan is managed in WP4, which has the role in the project in terms of communicating and disseminating Key Results to target stakeholders (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Positioning of WP4 in SWForum.eu

Input for WP4 activities will come from all other WPs:

- ▣ WP 2 – Cross-fertilisation and mapping
 - Cross-fertilization Workshops organisation (T2.1)
 - Online landscape project radar (T2.2)
 - Online hub of project mini-sites (T2.3)
- ▣ WP 3 - Sustainable SWForum.eu and Research & Innovation Roadmaps
 - Landscape report on software research, digital infrastructures, cybersecurity (T3.1)
 - Coordination of the Research & Innovation Roadmaps (T3.2)
 - Definition and creation of a Governance structure and business model (T3.3)
- ▣ WP 4 – Communication, Dissemination and MTRL
 - Communication and Dissemination (T4.1)
 - MTRL maturity growth for best practices & technology transfer (T4.2)
 - Engagement with industry and with end-user adoption (T4.3)
- ▣ WP 5 – Ethics requirements

3 SWForum.eu Stakeholder Groups

This section provides an outline of the stakeholders as well as the objectives and expectations for the target audiences identified. At the highest level, there are two major groupings involved: 1) the EU ICT Ecosystem, and 2) Policy-making actors. Cross-cutting over these groupings of the major stakeholders is the focus on the three topical pillars of SWForum.eu: software engineering, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity. Taken together, these groupings and pillars form the SWForum ecosystem of interest.

Within the EU ICT Ecosystem grouping, the primary sub-groupings identified are **Tech SMEs / Start-ups; Universities and Research Technology Offices; Large software industry; R&I projects; Vertical industries; and End users.**

Within the grouping of Policy Makers, the primary sub-groupings identified are actors responsible for **policy within relevant EC Units; National Initiatives; Top-Level Standardisation & Regulatory Bodies; and Sector-related Authorities and Associations.**

SWForum.eu will adopt a comprehensive approach, involving these stakeholders from the outset of the project.

3.1 Tech SMEs and Start-ups

Figure 3: Technology SMEs and Start-ups

Talent acquisition from Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), Start-ups, and Spin-offs and mid-caps (Figure 3) will be of paramount relevance. SMEs are among the prime innovators in software technologies and processes and must have their voices heard. SWForum.eu will prioritize their representation to ensure their backgrounds and needs (technical, business, policy-related) are properly reflected in the forum.

How they will benefit from SWForum.eu. SMEs are the locomotive of European industry, and this is truer than ever in software related industries, where innovation has consistently been spearheaded by the SMEs in areas ranging from machine vision to new DevOps lifecycle processes (to cite one example the entire agile movement was driven by SMEs, not the larger actors). A vigorous participation of SMEs in SWForum.eu will have a significant positive effect on its overall impact both on software technologies in general and on the software SME ecosystem in Europe.

The list below collects samples of channels specifically selected to reach out to this stakeholder group: AMETIC, Cap Digital, Digital SME Alliance, EIT Digital, European Business and Innovation Centres Network (EBN), Enterprise Europe Network (EEN), Enterprise Ireland, FIWARE

Foundation, F6S Network - Portugal, Innovate UK, INTEROP-VLAB, LINKS Foundation, Pan-European Network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), SMEs United. NetWorld2020 SME WG (5G). Innovation Radar – DSM online map.

3.2 Universities and Research Technology Offices

Academic and research partners represent an outstanding source of talent in software technologies. However, European policy makers have underlined the significant gap in the transfer of R&D results into market uptake and stressed the need to improve mutual awareness and cooperation between regulators, innovators, academia and the research communities.

How they will benefit from SWForum.eu. SWForum.eu will invest efforts to identify and engage with European and national funded projects with a clear mandate to generate market impact. With TECNALIA's involvement in EARTO, this ensures that the research community is implied directly in our efforts within SWForum.eu. The network of UOXF and POLIMI are also key in this respect.

In addition to a very large pool of universities and research centres, the consortium will extend its links to the European Council for Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (EURODOC) to cover the European Consortium of Innovative Universities; League of European Research Universities; European University Association.

3.3 Large software industry

The major European software industry actors are already heavily involved in initiatives to improve the positioning of Europe in the overall global software scene. For this reason alone, it is important that SWForum.eu liaise with the principal actors from large industry, in order to ensure that their ongoing efforts are reflected in the direction and activities of the Forum.

How they will benefit from SWForum.eu. Even the large software industry players in Europe have a need to expose and promote their interests within a larger and more diverse context than their own individual channels can provide. SWForum.eu will give them this context, providing a platform and forum in which they can meet with other major representatives of the European software industry, including those coming from sectors outside of their own particular domain of interest, as well as members of the European policy making community whose help they would like to enlist to influence the direction of software strategy in Europe.

We will ensure that large industry representatives are recruited into the forum. Given the active participation of both CONCEPTIVITY and TECNALIA in the Board of Directors of the European Organisation for Security and the European Cyber Security Organisation, the large players in the software industry are already being implicated in the efforts which will be undertaken by SWForum.eu.

3.4 Research and Innovation projects

EC-funded projects will form the core constituency that will populate the EU Project Radar instrument of SWForum.eu.

How they will benefit from SWForum.eu. Experience with the Project Radar tool together with the project mini-sites in previous (CloudWatch) and ongoing (Cybersecurity.eu) projects has demonstrated the level of outreach can be achieved by R&I projects that normally do not have access to such powerful mechanisms for showcasing their results and ambitions. This is especially true of software-oriented projects, many of which have significant cross-cutting value

which, however, often renders it difficult to insert them in a suitably defined outreach vehicle. SWForum.eu was created for them.

Although clearly the R&I projects that will be accepted within the same ICT-50-2020 Call as SWForum.eu will be key targets, SWForum.eu will cast a wide net across EU-funded projects to ensure that the relevant technologies and sectors are adequately represented within the radar. For example, synergies will be created with funded projects on cybersecurity and other relevant technologies, drawing on existing links to PPP and ETP associations, and collaborations across these stakeholders. This brings the potential for engagement with projects falling under multiple umbrellas, such as 5G deployment or infrastructures for transnational public administration interaction (e.g. the Once Only Principle infrastructure projects). Furthermore, with the “Booster” projects being led by TRUST-IT (e.g. the ongoing Horizon Results Booster), we can involve a large and comprehensive set of relevant projects to build upon in SWForum.eu.

3.5 Vertical industries

SWForum.eu aims to broaden the spectrum of profiles, including those vertical industries investing resources in adoption of advanced software technologies and digital infrastructures (e.g. sectors like eHealth, connected and automated vehicles, smart energy or manufacturing, all of which are particularly sensitive to cybersecurity concerns).

How they will benefit from SWForum.eu. Today, no vertical sector is unaffected by software, and we now speak routinely of autos as “computers on wheels” and airplanes as “flying computers”. Important advances in software are being made within the vertical industries – consider telecommunications and mission-critical systems as one example. But the very vertical nature of these industries tends to create silos that make it difficult for verticals to establish cross-sector relationships and to subsequently cross-fertilize. SWForum.eu will provide such opportunities.

The outreach in this category will also include liaison with sector-oriented standardisation task forces, which are central to achieving reliable, certifiable software products and systems in safety/security critical sectors. Examples include the CEN-CENELEC Sector Forum for Healthcare Standards¹, CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Coordination Group on Smart Grid², CEN-CENELEC Coordination Group on eMobility³, or the CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Coordination Group on Smart and Sustainable cities and communities⁴, 3GPP SA3 (security)⁵ and SA6 (mission-critical applications)⁶, which also covers demanding vertical industry needs.

3.6 Policy makers within relevant EC units

Those responsible in relevant units within the Commission for the formulation of policy regarding future directions for Europe with respect to the main pillars of emphasis in SWForum.eu will be reached out to in various forms over the duration of the project – through the road-mapping activities, focused events, etc.

How they will benefit from SWForum.eu. Policy makers within the EU and in particular within the Commission are soliciting authoritative inputs from the communities represented by the

¹ CEN-CENELEC Sector Forum for Healthcare Standards. <https://www.cen.eu/work/Sectors/Healthcare/>

² CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Coordination Group on Smart Grid. <https://www.cencenelec.eu/standards/Topics/Smartgrid/>

³ CEN-CENELEC Coordination Group on eMobility. <https://www.cencenelec.eu/standards/Topics/eMobility/>

⁴ CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Coordination Group on Smart and Sustainable cities and communities. <https://www.cencenelec.eu/standards/Topics/Smarthouse/>

⁵ <https://www.3gpp.org/specifications-groups/sa-plenary/sa3-security/home>.

⁶ <https://www.3gpp.org/specifications-groups/sa-plenary/sa6-mission-critical-applications/home>.

three pillars of SWForum.eu (software engineering, infrastructures, cybersecurity) in order to determine future directions for related policy decisions. SWForum.eu has organised instruments such as policy briefs and road mapping specifically for the purpose of providing such guidance.

The consortium members collectively bring an extensive portfolio of contacts within relevant Units through their previous and ongoing activities, beyond Directorate E and H to cover Smart and Sustainable Growth (DG Regional and Urban Policy); Smart Mobility and Living; Knowledge Management and Innovative Systems; Innovation and Start-ups Unit; Innovation, FinTech and Blockchain; Cybersecurity - Research Executive Agency; ICT Standardization.

3.7 National Initiatives

Several Member States have important national initiatives in numerous areas that influence policy both at the MS level and the EU level, such as national policies for digital infrastructures and communication.

How they will benefit from SWForum.eu. The nature of national initiatives is such that there is always a risk of silos emerging, both in technical and in policy directions. While this can be understandable in the context of national priorities within a Member State, it is always beneficial to be able to discuss and confront one’s own initiatives with representatives from other national initiatives within the EU, to seek and obtain policy-level cross-fertilisation and, when appropriate, also technical cross-fertilisation.

The following are examples of the channels available for outreach to this stakeholder group: The consortium will leverage its public-sector stakeholders, such as ECSO, e.g. AT: Federal Chancellery of Austria (BKA). BE: Belgian Institute for Post and Telecommunication (BIPT); Centre pour la Cybersécurité Belgique (CCB). BU: Permanent Representation of the Republic of Bulgaria to the European Union; State eGovernment Agency (SeGA). CY: Office of the Commissioner of Electronic Communications and Postal Regulation (OCECPR). CZ: National Cyber and Information Security Authority of the Czech Republic (NCISA); Národní agentura pro komonikacni a informacni technologie (NAKIT). DE: Federal Office for Information Security (BSI). EE: Ministry of Defence of the Republic of Estonia. ES: Spanish National Cyber Security Institute (INCIBE); State Secretariat for Telecommunications and Information Society (SETSI); Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology of Spain (CDTI). FI: The National Emergency Supply Agency (NESA). FR: Agence Nationale de la Sécurité des Systemes d’Information (ANSSI). GR: General Secretary of Digital Policy, National Cyber Security Authority (NCSA). IT: Ministry of Economic Development (MISE). NL: Ministry of Security and Justice. NO: Research Council of Norway (RCN). PL: Ministry of Digital Affairs. RO: CERT-RO. SE: Verket för Innovationssystem (Vinnova). UK: Department for Digital Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS).

3.8 Top-level standardisation and regulatory bodies

Figure 4: Top level Standards Development Organisations

Several relevant bodies (Figure 4) have been established that make important policy-related contributions, such as ENISA in the cybersecurity domain, and 3GPP in the network communications domain. IEEE is an important player in the establishment of software engineering standards.

How they will benefit from SWForum.eu. Contribution to international standards and regulations is a long-term process that generally unfolds over a long horizon – certainly longer than the duration of the SWForum.eu CSA. Nevertheless, SWForum.eu will contribute to this process by providing a forum for cross-fertilisation among representatives participating in standards development, which they may then incorporate into their own respective committee work. This will help to promote the development of robust international software-related standards that help the EU software industry to remain competitive through standards-supported innovation.

The SWForum.eu consortium features partners who work within numerous top-level standardisation committees and initiatives. At least two partners (POLIMI and TRUST-IT) are active in IEEE software-related initiatives. Other partners are active in ENISA and telecom-related developers of technical software specifications such as the 3G PP.

3.9 Sector-related Authorities and Associations

In specific vertical sectors, authorities (in particular, certification authorities) and sector associations (such as the 5G Automotive Association) make significant contributions to policy directions concerning the main pillars of SWForum.eu and must be included within its outreach. Collaborations and strong links to major standards organizations, including a network of over 1300 chairs and specialists, will enable SWForum.eu to track relevant sector-related standardization.

3.10 Summary: a broad range of synergies

The overarching principle governing stakeholder outreach will involve striving to maximize synergies over a broad range of relevant stakeholders and sectors, exploiting the manifold collective set of contacts of the consortium partners that form one of the most important assets of the project (Figure 5).

Figure 5: A sample of synergies

4 Rollout of the SWForum.eu Mini-Sites

The SWForum.eu Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan sets out specific measures for a European Software Observatory that will create a strong software culture across vertical sectors as the basis for a competitive EU ecosystem.

SWForum.eu will be creating a comprehensive compilation of EU-funded research projects on software topics. It will be created specifically to facilitate information transfer, communication and cross-pollination. This will be supported by the rollout of a set of so-called “mini-sites”, a communications and dissemination instrument already deployed successfully in previous projects such as Cyberwatching.eu⁷. The key idea behind the mini-sites is to provide a means for a user examining the Project Radar to find out immediately more information about a project that has stimulated interest on the Radar itself. The mini-site represents a compact and efficient first step in gathering more information about a project.

As the name suggests: a *mini-site* is a smaller, reduced version of a full-fledged project website, which nevertheless contains fundamental information about the project, including links to further information about the project for the interested reader (e.g., a link to the primary project website).

A fully validated workflow used in previous projects is followed in order to populate the mini-sites on the SWForum.eu platform. It consists of the following steps, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Mini-site rollout workflow

- Profiling.** SWForum.eu consortium members will identify the appropriate list of software projects, contacting these projects, confirming their interest, and arranging for the creation of their mini-sites on the SWForum.eu platform.

⁷ www.cyberwatching.eu

- **Autonomous management.** Initially, creation of the project mini-sites will be executed by the SWForum.eu team, by providing project overviews, results, news and events, project reports, deliverables, videos, demos etc. Over time, the R&I projects will be able to autonomously manage and enhance their respective mini-sites as they see fit, without needing intervention from SWForum.eu personnel. This is a powerful incentive for the projects, giving them an additional dissemination channel to the entire SWForum.eu community.
- **Personalised user experience for each mini-site.** Each mini-site will be tailored to different stakeholder needs with fast and easy access to a wealth of software practical guides and insights into multiple formats, such as SEO-based texts, videos, webinars, leading to the activation of the Online Forum and its Catalogue of Services.
- **Cross-project communication.** This will offer an extra channel for project visibility to promote events, news, results and be featured on the SWForum.eu programme “Project of the week”.

5 Communication, dissemination, marketing, and stakeholder engagement activities

Communication is key and the success of SWForum.eu will be attained by promoting and ensuring its visibility in both online and offline channels, building the SWForum.eu brand through a coordinated marketing, dissemination and engagement strategy. The SWForum.eu team will work continuously to enhance the existing communication strategy in key elements such as branding visibility, exploitation of media channels, and a widened audience together. This will go hand-in-hand with the development of synergies, both internally and externally, for the overall success of the project.

This section provides an outline of the communication, dissemination, marketing and stakeholder engagement with plans on how to engage and communicate with them and includes associated KPIs for monitoring the activities and the impact.

5.1 Visual identity and branding

SWForum.eu follows the key guidelines listed below:

- Human centred;
- Balance between “digital & analogue”;
- Evolution vs. Revolution;
- Readable and recognisable in any circumstances;
- Wide colour range;
- Fashionable;
- Highly modular & responsive.

These guidelines are incorporated into the *SWForum.eu Brand Guideline* document (first version September 2020).

The first way to “communicate” the project is the identification of the project logo. The SWForum.eu logo (Figure 7), with its cascading yet interlocking (united by shades of blue) plates, transmits a feeling of *community*, the guiding objective of the project.

Figure 7. SWForum.eu logo

Different SWForum.eu logos (Figure 8) have been created for use in different contexts (social media, website, and printed material).

Figure 8: Different SWForum.eu logo variations

Similarly, a set of logos for the different assets generated by SWForum.eu has been designed, for even more precise branding according to asset type (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Sample logos of different SWForum.eu Assets

A set of promotional materials will be produced for the project, including among others, project flyers & social media cards and images, and posters. An appropriate mix between digital and physical media formats will be chosen according to the demands and consequences of the situation caused by COVID-19. Currently, the emphasis is on digital media, which will be ready for immediate deployment in January 2021.

5.2 SWForum.eu platform and website

The SWForum.eu website is the central communication and dissemination channel of the project. It will be hosting several project assets, which will form the website structure and are highly visible on the homepage which will be continuously evolving as the project results and assets are released or published.

The SWForum.eu website (<https://www.swforum.eu/>) is powered by a **professional CMS (Drupal)** and has a modern look and an intuitive structure. Menus and submenus are designed

to improve the user experience and facilitate navigation through the whole website, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: SWForum.eu menu structure

The current landing page has clear entry points on the homepage for the two main assets targeting the research and innovation (R&I) projects, the end-users and industry community. Project assets and results relevant to these stakeholders will be positioned in these entry points.

- R&I Projects
 - SW Project Observatory
 - European Landscape Project Radar
- End-users and Industry
 - SW Experts Forum Platform

Of course, the website is destined to expand and become more articulated as the project progresses.

The website includes an entry point to the **SWForum.eu Intranet**, an Alfresco⁸-based repository for document storage and interchange provided by Project Coordinator TECNALIA.

Content Driven Approach

The communication, marketing and engagement plan will concentrate its efforts on copywriting and producing engaging, stimulating and impactful content. The SWForum.eu editorial planning will include regular publication of updates covering the Project Radar and Mini-Sites platform, SWForum.eu webinars and events with their output, as well as other events relevant for the target stakeholders such as news pieces, interviews and spotlights on projects taken up in the Radar and Mini-Sites.

⁸ <https://www.alfresco.com/>

SWForum.Eu And The European Software Ecosystem: We Need To Talk

15 October 2020

The European software ecosystem needs to avoid the risk of fragmentation exactly at a moment in which increased *integration* is needed. How? Let us count the ways:

Software A Strategic Priority For The European Commission

27 October 2020

On 21 October, the European Commission approved its new Open Source Software Strategy 2020-2023, a part of the overarching Digital Strategy of the Commission and contributing to the Digital Europe programme. SWForum.eu, a project funded by the European Commission Horizon 2020 Programme, will set out the landscape of European projects in Software Engineering, Digital Infrastructure and Cybersecurity, as well as bring together a wide forum of researchers, industry, policy makers, and end users, including those in the Open Source domain.

Figure 11: Examples of news items

Table 2: Content Production KPIs (source: SWForum.eu DoA)

KPI	KPI for the overall project
Content Production	Min. 4 new content items per month; 1000 monthly sessions, 500 users, 1500 page views
Brochures, flyers, posters, roll-up banners, slide decks etc. - tailored to different audiences	Min. 10 per year
Informative and marketing PRs to be distributed to specific Press & Media Channels.	Min. 1 per year

5.3 Social media campaigns

SWForum.eu is using two key social networks, Twitter and LinkedIn, first of all, to build its community and promote the open calls, and ultimately to communicate all the outputs and results. Twitter is mainly used for real-time updates and to promote event-centred activities, but also as a tool to engage projects for our Project Radar and Mini-Sites.

At the time of writing, the SWForum.eu Twitter account (@SWforumEU) is constructing a solid base of followers targeting profiles that are more interested in the SWForum.eu fields of expertise such as Software Engineering, Digital Infrastructures, Cybersecurity and other relevant fields.

Figure 12: Twitter account header

LinkedIn will be mainly used to onboard new relevant stakeholders, send target messages and create and follow discussion groups. At the moment of writing, SWForum.eu’s LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/swforum.eu>) already has over 200 followers.

Figure 13: LinkedIn Header

Table 3: Social Media Strategy KPIs (source: SWForum.eu DoA)

Activity	KPI
Twitter	400 Tweets and 400 Twitter followers by M30
LinkedIn	500 followers by M30

5.4 Newsletters

The SWForum.eu project will use the newsletters as a regular tool to send selected information to its subscribers. The main focus will cover the SWForum.eu project’s activities and status of the calls, to engage potential stakeholders, and to share events and dissemination material.

Table 4: Newsletter KPIs (source: SWForum.eu DoA)

Activity	KPI M10	KPI M20	KPI M30
10 newsletters circulated to subscribed community members	100 target recipients	250 target recipients	500 target recipients

5.5 Videos

As part of the communication strategy, SWForum.eu will create videos and video pills as a more impactful medium to quickly and efficiently communicate with the project audience and stakeholders.

Table 5: Video KPIs (source: SWForum.eu DoA)

Activity	KPI M10	KPI M20	KPI M30
Informative and marketing videos produced by professional in house team.	1	2	4

6 SWForum.eu Events and Third-Party Events

Over its 30-month lifetime, SWForum.eu will organise webinars and workshops, including the Cross-Fertilisation Workshops.

Each event is published in the “News and Events” section of the website, accessible from the top-bar menu, with a different tag according to whether it is a Webinar, a SWForum.eu event (including events SWForum.eu took part in and the SWForum.eu Cross-Fertilisation Workshops) or a “related” event (more generic events related to the topics addressed by SWForum.eu but not organised by SWForum.eu: this section includes, but is not limited to, the events involving SWForum.eu and its related projects). Each event published on the website is then shared via the SWForum.eu LinkedIn and Twitter pages, as well as on the newsletter.

Figure 14: Events area on the SWForum.eu website

6.1 SWForum.eu workshops

One of the main outputs of SWForum.eu is the organisation of “**Cross-Fertilization Workshops**” over the 30 months of the project, where stakeholders coming from the different communities and expertise will gather to focus on topics such as software technologies for the cloud computing continuum, cognitive cloud and federated cloud and digital (secure) infrastructures. Other themes will be included based on the results of the first workshop and on the inputs gathered from the stakeholders SWForum.eu will come in contact with. The results will be in joint papers for joint policy.

The cross-fertilization workshops are intended to foster an open discussion forum, where stakeholders with different interests, technology maturity (e.g. early adopters, early majority) and industry (academia, RTO, SME, LE) will come together. They will be used as the main channels to facilitate awareness and to close the gap between industry and research. Initially **three cross-fertilization workshops** are planned. These will consist of a public event, open to the whole software community (Multi-stakeholder forum), and a closed event (Research policy Forum), more focused on the interaction of the projects funded by the unit E2 and any other

units the European Commission deems appropriate (e.g. H1 and H2, C1...). The objectives of the public and open events of these cross-fertilization workshops are 1) to close the gap between research and industry, by transferring knowledge from researchers to the industry but also by transferring the needs of the industry towards the research community and the policy-makers, 2) to validate and receive feedback on the innovation roadmaps proposed in the software technology, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity arena. The closed events will include not only the exchange of best practices, results and means for further collaboration, but also policy-related aspects such as to contribute to the research and innovation roadmaps. These events are crucial activities for community building and for the projects to disseminate research results among software engineering research practitioners and to find opportunities to collaborate and engage.

Due to the current Covid-19 emergency, the workshops (at least in the initial part of the project), will be transformed into online events, with the first one to be organised around M5, depending on the availability of the participants.

6.2 SWForum.eu webinars

The SWForum.eu event suite also includes hosting 10 webinars dedicated to presenting the technologies, methodologies and techniques developed in the context of research projects with the aim of bringing research results closer to the market.

On top of these and complementary to them, SWForum.eu will organize 4 educational webinars aimed at preparing projects for their market and technology readiness strategic planning. Communicated as mandatory educational material for the projects in the SWForum.eu Radar, the webinars will be structured to help them make the right preparations before embarking on regular MTRL self-assessment activities. The starting point will be a walkthrough followed by a series of deep dives zooming in on IPR, licensing, contracting, partnering and other business processes necessary to increase market readiness of the innovated product.

6.3 SWForum.eu podcasts

Podcasts are a very popular medium for learning, and particularly useful as an additional communication channel during this time of Covid-19. They can be efficiently produced and convey information on topics of great interest in a compact medium.

Podcasts may also be employed as a means for promoting particularly engaged members of the Living Forum – effectively providing an engagement incentive, rewarding active participation with increased exposure. It will also be a means of engaging new software communities by inviting relevant experts to feature on the podcast.

All podcasts will be promoted with a news piece on the website, as well as dedicated social media posts on LinkedIn and Twitter. These social media posts will also include short snippets of the podcast in video form with subtitles in order to catch the attention of those who are scrolling through social media feeds and create interest in listening to the whole episode, to which a link will be included in the post.⁹

The first SWForum.eu podcast¹⁰ was published on 17 November 2020, featuring the SWForum.eu project coordinator Leire Orue-Echevarria, who gave a high-level overview of the project, its objectives, challenges and impacts. The banner for the first episode can be seen below. The next podcast is planned to feature an expert (TBC) from the European Open Source

⁹ <https://twitter.com/SWforumEU/status/1330783484139409410>

¹⁰ <https://swforum.eu/news-events/news/swforumeu-launches-podcast>

Software community who will share about Open Source and how its intersections with SWForum.eu, and will be published in January 2021.

Figure 15: First SWForum.eu podcast

6.4 Third Party Events

Third-Party Events are external events (not organised by SWForum.eu) relevant for the project due to their pertinence with the topics addressed by SWForum.eu, or their possibility to be exploited to gain visibility, simply by taking part or by promoting them through the website and on the social media pages. Presence at related external events will help to further develop the SWForum.eu community, through presenting of the opportunity offered by the Living Forum, Project Radar, and Mini-Sites. Involvement in SWForum.eu events will facilitate multi-stakeholder engagement, allowing secondary stakeholders to be reached through the various SWForum.eu channels.

Figure 16: 3rd-party event

An example of this type of external event is the *EU Open Source Policy Summit 2021*, scheduled for 05 February 2021, and transformed into an online event in order to cope with the Covid-19 emergency. These events are still included in the related events section on the website, in that they are not organised directly by SWForum.eu, but are pertinent to the topics addressed by the project. The same communication activities will be carried out for relevant third-party events as for SWForum.eu events.

- One event news piece on the website;
- Social media posts;
- Live tweeting at the event;
- Communication package including fliers, pop-up banner (for a physical event), and Institutional Presentation.

An example of live reporting on external events is the participation of J. Favaro of Trust-IT in an invited panel session at the *19th Intl. Conference on Software Reuse* on 03 December 2020, which was live tweeted and followed up by a news piece on the website.

A living document, shared by the entire consortium, is used as the main tracker for participation in events, both internal and external. A snapshot of the current state of this document is shown in the Appendix.

7 Communication Toolkit

The communication toolkit aims to ensure the timely delivery of high-quality materials and tools supporting stakeholder engagement with messages tailored to various levels of knowledge. The communication toolkit aims to align and facilitate the engagement and communication for SWForum.eu project partners and multipliers. The toolkit is KPI-based for communications and stakeholder engagement, as described in the following tables. Those KPIs flagged with an asterisk (“*”) originate directly in the Description of Work. Those KPIs flagged with a plus sign (“+”) originate in our own experience and best practices in similar contexts.

Table 6: Comms Toolkit – Content Production

Content Production	KPIs for the overall project
Distribution of SWForum.eu press releases targeting special interest groups and potential applicants to the Mini-Sites.	Min. 1 new press release per year*
Articles specifically written for CORDIS RESEARCH EU, CORDIS Results Packs, and Digital Single Market blogs for timely information about SWForum.eu activities.	2 CORDIS articles per year+ 2 DSM blog publications per year+

Table 7: Comms Toolkit – promotional materials

Flyers, factsheets, infographics, roll-ups	KPIs for the overall project
Brochures, flyers, posters, roll-up banners, slide decks etc. - tailored to different audiences	Minimum 10 per year*

Table 8: Comms Toolkit – videos

Videos	KPIs for the overall project
Informative and marketing videos produced by professional in house team.	Minimum 4*

Table 9: Comms Toolkit – newsletters and email marketing

Videos	KPIs for the overall project
Newsletter creation	10 by M30+
Newsletter outreach	500 recipients reached by M30+
Email marketing	According to promotional needs+

The Social Media strategy is designed in tiers, each of them aligned with the promotional and communication campaigns laid out in Section 5:

Table 10: Comms Toolkit – social media strategy

Social media activity	KPIs for the overall project
Overall social media connections	400 overall connections (Twitter + LinkedIn) per year*
Webinars	10 with a minimum of 40 attendees per webinar*
Twitter	400 Tweets, 400 Twitter followers by M30+

8 Monitoring activities and measuring impact

Measurable impacts (KPIs) are tracked on a monthly basis through an online dashboard (Figure 17) monitoring the visibility, engagement, and dissemination potential of online activities in automated software which extracts, analyses, and visualises the selected figures and compares them with the given KPIs. The tools offered by each of the major channels are used in this task: Google Analytics; Twitter Analytics; LinkedIn Analytics. Note that these tools permit real-time updates. Analytics on the website will arrive after Month 6 when the official website is launched.

Figure 17: KPI monitoring dashboard display

9 Risk Assessment & Mitigation Plan

In addition to the official deliverable D1.2 *Risk assessment and contingency plan*, a supplementary extension is provided in this section related specifically to WP4 risks. The impact of COVID-19 is particularly relevant for WP4. Different scenarios may be hypothesized:

- Scenario 1: the crisis ends in the Summer of 2021;
- Scenario 2: the crisis ends in the Winter of 2021-2022.

(Here, “crisis ends” means that cross-border movements become possible again.)

A third hypothesis is also possible: COVID-19 will probably have long-term impact, and calls for new approaches to stakeholder engagement. The main conclusions are summarised below.

- **SWForum.eu context 1 – Stakeholder engagement:** Impossibility of running workshops and face-to-face meetings with partners.
 - Partners have been affected, e.g. forced to rely on smart working and their own computing/network resources, making coordination of activities generally more difficult.
- **SWForum.eu context 2- Dissemination of results:** Blind period for conferences and opportunities for dissemination through presentations, networking and publishing.
 - SWForum.eu will certainly lose several such opportunities though some may be recoverable later in 2021 or in 2022.
 - Cancelled events targeted by SWForum.eu: *situation being monitored at this time.*
 - Postponed events: *Situation currently being monitored.*
- **Evolution of COVID-19:** There is much speculation about the evolution of COVID-19 and the so-called “return to reality”. The latest evidence points to the low likelihood of physical events taking place in 2021 despite the more optimistic views of the scientific community, while industry fora (e.g. the 5G Automotive Association, an IT infrastructure related group) and most standards organisations have cancelled physical events until further notice and probably well into 2021.

New forms of engagement are clearly needed, whether they be **webinars, virtual events** or other formats, e.g. **podcasts**), considering also the long-term need to protect the safety of all the community.

While many activities in WP4 will continue unaffected, albeit not under ideal conditions, those that rely on face-to-face engagement and/or inputs from the end-user community, which is constrained by COVID-19 crisis management and blanket travel bans, will suffer a greater impact.

However, no project can stand still. To ensure impact for the SWForum.eu stakeholder workshops as critical events for collecting feedback from stakeholders:

- It has been decided to organise the first workshop as a virtual event in February 2021.
- To overcome barriers to direct stakeholder engagement, the number of planned webinars will be increased.
- The plan for M13-30 will also take into account the need for future virtual workshops and/or webinars given the uncertainty that still surrounds the pandemic at the time of writing this document.

10 Conclusions

This document is agreed upon between all the SWForum.eu partners and it constitutes a pragmatic plan to deliver a series of activities to which all partners – with the different levels of effort foreseen by the SWForum.eu work plan – commit to contribute.

WP4 is responsible for monitoring the execution of the activities and to ensure partners' active contribution according to their different roles and effort in the project WPs and tasks.

Concerning targets, KPIs and the planned activities, the Communication Plan is, in effect, a “living document”.

This Communication Plan document will be updated with two more iterations over the course of the project. For a comprehensive overview in context of the communications activities over the first six months of the project, see Figure 18 (*next page*).

Figure 18: SWForum.eu overall communications timeline

APPENDIX: Current List of Events

SWForum, as part of its mission, curates a selection of relevant events according to the three categories identified and described in Section 6.

Above all due to the uncertain situation caused by the pandemic crisis (see Section 9), the list of events is in a constant state of flux at the time of writing, as organisers decide whether and how to transform physical events into virtual or mixed-mode events. Nevertheless, we felt it was important to commence early to create the selection and put monitoring mechanisms in place.

Table 11: Events organised by SWForum.eu

Events	Date	Name and Type of audience	Countries Addressed	Size of audience	People attending	Status	Last update
First SWForum.eu Cross-Fertilization Workshop	Week 2, February 2021	Principally researchers, secondary target industry	EU	100 (virtual)	Representatives of all consortium partners	Ongoing preparation	Dec-21

As Table 11 shows, at the time of writing there is a single event planned that is directly organised by SWForum.eu – the first cross-fertilization workshop (see Section 6.1). This will evolve quickly as the various results of SWForum.eu (including the Project Radar, Forum, and so forth) emerge.

Table 12: Events at which SWForum.eu will be present

Events	Date	Name and Type of audience	Countries Addressed	Size of audience	People attending	Status	Last update
19th International Conference on Software and Systems Reuse	3-Dec-20	SW Reuse, software researchers and practitioners	Global	100	J. Favaro / Trust-IT	Attended	3 Dec 20
Europe's Digital Decade: Empowered by Open Source	5-Nov-20	SW practitioners, policy makers, researchers	Europe and USA	130	J. Favaro / Trust-IT, J. Alonso and L. Orue-Echevarria / Tecnalía	Attended	Europe's Digital Decade: Empowered by Open Source
Turning Ethical AI into Technical Reality – The Role of Open Source and Standardisation	18-Nov-20	SW practitioners, policy makers, researchers	Europe and USA	100	J. Favaro / Trust-IT	Attended	18 Nov 20
The EU Open Source Policy Summit 2021	5-Feb-21	SW practitioners, policy makers, researchers	Europe and USA	130	J. Favaro / Trust-IT	Attending	The EU Open Source Policy Summit 2021

In contrast, Table 12 reports more events, some of which have already seen active participation by SWForum.eu consortium members. This list will likewise evolve as consortium members, who are active in events in their own respective fields of specialisation (e.g. software engineering, cybersecurity) begin to organise their participation in the conference of those sectors, together with planning their presentations of SWForum.eu activities in those conferences.

Table 13: Events at which SWForum.eu will be present

Events	Date	Name and Type of audience	Countries Addressed	Size of audience	People attending	Status	Last update
International Conference on Digital Infrastructure	May-21	Academia, scientists, researchers	Global, EU	100	TBD	TBD	Dec-21
International Conference on Software Engineering	25-28 May 2021	Academia, scientists, researchers, industry	Global, EU	1000	TBD	TBD	Dec-21
The 48th Annual ACM SIGPLAN Symposium on Principles of Programming Languages	17-Jan-21	Academia, scientists, researchers, industry	Global, EU	100	TBD	TBD	Dec-21
OSS 2021 — 17th International Conference on Open Source Systems	12-May-21	Industry	Global, EU	500	TBD	TBD	Dec-21
IEEE Cyber Security and Resilience Conference	26-Jul-21	Academia, scientists, researchers, industry	Global, EU	150	TBD	TBD	Dec-21
42nd IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy	23-May-21	Academia, scientists, researchers, industry	Global, EU	200	TBD	TBD	Dec-21
The 2021 IEEE Conference on Dependable and Secure Computing	30-Jan-21	Academia, scientists, researchers, industry	Global, EU	175	TBD	TBD	Dec-21

Finally, Table 13 lists a selection of events that have been identified to date as being relevant to the aims of SWForum.eu. Most of them have not yet decided upon the actual configuration with respect to virtual/physical organization. Some are associated with the specialization sectors of SWForum.eu consortium members (e.g. ICSE 2021). The list will certainly evolve and be updated at the next iteration of this deliverable.